

Bridging the scales through the analysis of neural complexity

Bridging scales with complexity

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Abstract

Understanding brain activity across multiple scales is essential for unraveling the complexities of neural function. From the macroscopic to the microscopic level, the brain exhibits diverse dynamics, shaped by billions of neurons and their intricate synaptic connections. However, navigating across these scales presents significant challenges due to technical and conceptual limitations. Complexity analysis provides a promising framework to address these challenges, offering insights into how neural activity spans across scales and how alterations, such as those induced by drugs, impact brain function. This article explores the use of complexity analysis to study brain activity, emphasizing its role in navigating neural scales and elucidating the intricate relationship between microscopic neuronal dynamics and macroscopic brain function. Through this perspective, we aim to foster a deeper understanding of brain complexity and its implications for neuroscience research.

Keywords: EEG, LFP, sleep, REM, ibogaine, urethane, entropy

Introduction

A multitude of scales characterizes brain activity (Buzsáki, 2004; He and Raichle, 2009; Lewis et al., 2024, 2015). The brain comprises billions of neurons, each with thousands of synaptic connections, forming a vast and interconnected network (Binzegger et al., 2004; He and Raichle, 2009; Sporns et al., 2005). As a result, brain activity encompasses a myriad of scales ranging from the macroscopic to the microscopic (Fig. 1A). At the macroscopic level,

the activity of the different brain areas can be studied through the lens of functional magnetic resonance imaging (fMRI) (He and Raichle, 2009; Ogawa et al., 1990) or electroencephalography (EEG) (Berger, 1929; Bisiacchi et al., 2019), capturing the collective dynamics of large populations of neurons. At the mesoscale level, we encounter neuronal circuits, where diverse groups of neurons give rise to intricate networks that allow specific computations to occur (Buzsáki et al., 2012; Buzsáki and Wang, 2012; Douglas and Martin, 2004; Gonzalez et al., 2023; Luo, 2021). These networks are usually studied through local field potentials (LFP) (Herreras, 2016) and calcium imaging (Tian et al., 2009). Finally, at the microscopic scale, the firing patterns of individual neurons can be studied through patch-clamp recordings (Sakmann and Neher, 1984) or multi-electrode arrays (Jun et al., 2017). These techniques allow us to study how the precise timing and frequency of the spike trains encodes the basic information employed for diverse computations across scales.

Navigating across the neural scales is a hard problem (Bohara et al., 2018; Gao and Ganguli, 2015; Huang et al., 2021; Munn et al., 2023; Paninski and Cunningham, 2018; Scholtens and van den Heuvel, 2018; Sejnowski et al., 2014; Williamson et al., 2019). The difficulties arise from both technical and conceptual limitations, hindering our ability to connect observations across different levels of analysis. While whole-brain imaging modalities like fMRI offer excellent spatial resolution, they often lack the temporal resolution necessary to capture the rapid dynamics of individual neurons firing. Conversely, electrophysiological methods excel in recording the millisecond-scale temporal dynamics of neuronal activity but are constrained by their limited spatial coverage, typically focusing on small populations of neurons or even single cells. Noteworthy, novel optical methods, such as calcium or voltage imaging, promise to offer both high spatial and temporal resolution (Abdelfattah et al., 2019; Grinvald and Hildesheim, 2004; Stringer et al., 2019a, 2019b), but these methods are still not as widely employed in research and clinical context as the abovementioned ones.

Moreover, the brain operates through a hierarchical organization of interconnected circuits, where information is processed and integrated across multiple levels (Friston, 2005; Kiebel et al., 2008). Therefore, to fully understand the brain, one needs to know how changes in activity at the level of individual neurons translates into emergent phenomena at the level of neural circuits, and whole-brain dynamics. Furthermore, the dynamic nature of brain activity adds another layer of complexity. Neural activity is highly context-dependent, influenced by factors such as behavioral state, sensory input, and neuromodulatory signals (Adamantidis et al., 2007; Lee and Dan, 2012; Nir and de Lecea, 2023; Steinmetz et al., 2019; Stringer et al., 2019a, 2019b). Integrating these dynamic factors across scales presents a significant challenge, as the relationship between neural activity and behavior can be nonlinear and multifaceted.

In this article, we will offer a perspective on how the analysis of neural complexity offers a novel approach to studying brain activity across different scales. The text will be organized as follows: 1) We provide an overview of brain activity at different scales. 2) We demonstrate how the analysis of neural complexity enables navigation across these scales. 3) We present an example of how psychedelic and anesthetic drugs affect neural complexity. 4) We provide a proof-of-concept illustrating how changes at the microscopic scale can impact the macroscopic scale.

Main text

Brain patterns occur simultaneously at different temporal and spatial scales

Neural oscillations span a wide range of frequencies (Fig. 1B). Brain rhythms, observed for instance through ECoG (electrocorticography) and LFP recordings, span from slow delta waves (0.5-4 Hz), prominent during deep Non-REM sleep or slow wave sleep (SWS) (Massimini et al., 2004), to faster gamma oscillations (30-150 Hz), associated during wakefulness with sensory processing and cognitive tasks (Buzsáki and Draguhn, 2004; Buzsáki and Wang, 2012; Fernández-Ruiz et al., 2021; Gonzalez et al., 2023; Tort et al., 2009). Notably, these frequency bands follow a scale-free power-law $P(f) = f^{-\beta}$, with an exponent (β) close to 1 (commonly referred as pink noise or $1/f$ decay) (Donoghue et al., 2020; González et al., 2023; Lendner et al., 2020; Miller et al., 2009). Note that the power-law behavior can be evidenced and quantified by plotting the power spectrum on a log-log scale and fitting a linear model to the data. This $\sim 1/f$ decay is characteristic of a heavy-tail distribution, i.e., despite the contribution of the different bands decreasing with the frequency, high-frequency activity still contributes significantly to the field signal. Moreover, it is important to point out that frequency ranges (which delimit the frequency bands) increase as we move from the low to the high end of the spectrum (Buzsáki and Draguhn, 2004; González et al., 2020; Mondino et al., 2020), making the contribution of each band more similar in the overall recorded signal.

Figure 1. Different neural scales characterize brain activity. **A** Schematic representation of the different brain scales, from the macroscopic scale (the brain as an organ) to the mesoscopic (neural circuits in different brain areas) and to the microscopic (individual neurons). The brain image was obtained from <https://neuroscience-graphicdesign.com/>, the neural circuit was reproduced from (Stern et al., 2018), and the neuron was taken from Freepik.com. **B** LFP [ECoG] power spectrum from the frontal cortex [M1 cortex] during the states of Wake, SWS and REM sleep. The mean and its corresponding 95% confidence intervals are shown for each plot. **C** Example of a neuronal avalanche. The average inter-spike interval ISI is used to bin the raster plot (shaded rectangles), and the number of spikes per bin was counted. **D** Avalanche statistics for the neocortex (top) and hippocampus (bottom). Left: Distribution of avalanche duration. Middle: distribution of avalanche size. Right: avalanche size as a function of its duration. For each state (color coded), the mean distributions are shown in solid lines with a shaded area depicting the 95% confidence interval. Modified from (González et al., 2023).

Spiking activity in the brain also spans a wide temporal range (Fig. 1C). An example of this phenomena are neural avalanches, which describe spontaneous bursts of activity that propagate through neural networks, akin to the cascading effect of falling snowflakes in an avalanche (Beggs and Plenz, 2003; Bellay et al., 2015; Ribeiro et al., 2010). A neuronal avalanche starts after a time bin without spikes and finishes when another empty time bin is reached; these avalanches can occur at various temporal scales, from milliseconds to seconds (Fig. 1D), and involve the synchronized firing of large ensembles of neurons. Notably, avalanches exhibit scale-invariant properties, meaning that their size and duration distributions also behave as power-laws (Fig. 1D). Altogether, this scale-free behavior in oscillatory and spiking activity suggests that the brain operates near a critical point (Chialvo, 2010; Fontenele et al., 2019; Priesemann et al., 2014, 2013), where small perturbations can trigger large-scale cascades of activity, facilitating efficient information processing and integration.

Navigating the cortical scales by studying neural complexity

The previous section showed how brain activity (oscillations and spikes) exhibits a wide temporal arrangement and can be described by power-laws. This type of scaling often emerges in complex systems (Barabasi and Albert, 1999). Therefore, different tools have been devised over the decades to directly quantify the complexity of a system (Bandt and Pompe, 2002; Casali et al., 2013; Massimini et al., 2005; Tononi et al., 1994). In this section, we are going to show that by measuring neural complexity, it is possible to distinguish brain states across different recording scales.

Defining neural complexity can be a daunting challenge. Measuring it, on the other hand, often boils down to computing an entropy measure (e.g., permutation entropy, sample entropy, etc.) on a given brain activity time-series (Fig. 2). For instance, permutation entropy works by first converting the original time series into a sequence of ordinal patterns based on the relative ordering of data points within a defined window (Bandt and Pompe, 2002). Then, it calculates the probability distribution of these ordinal patterns. The Shannon entropy is then computed from this probability distribution, measuring the average uncertainty or randomness in the sequence of ordinal patterns. A higher permutation entropy value indicates greater complexity or irregularity in the time series, whereas a lower value suggests more regular and predictable behavior. Note that other metrics can also be applied

to a symbolic time-series to obtain complexity estimates, for instance, Lempel-Ziv, which measures data compressibility and often yields similar results to entropy-based measures (González et al., 2023; Lempel and Ziv, 1976; Mateos et al., 2020; Pascovich et al., 2022)

Figure 2. Measuring neural complexity. **Top:** The left panel shows an ECoG recording during wakefulness in a freely behaving rat. 5 seconds are shown; each trace corresponds to one cortical location. The middle panel exhibits the different possible ordinal patterns that can be obtained employing an embedding dimension = 3. That is all possible relative orderings of a single ECoG recording within a 3-point window. Thus, one transforms a continuous signal into a discrete sequence of ordinal patterns. The right panel shows the distribution of each ordinal pattern in a whole six-hour recording. Each color shows a different sleep state. Note that the purely increasing (1) or decreasing (6) ordinal patterns are the most common ones. The Shannon entropy is then computed from the ordinal pattern distribution. Modified from (González et al., 2019). **Bottom:** This panel shows how to obtain a synthetic LFP (sLFP). The sLFP is defined as the average of the convolutions between spike trains and a decaying exponential function. To the right we show examples of sLFP during Wake, SWS, and REM sleep population activity. The figures were modified from (González et al., 2023).

It is worth mentioning that most of these complexity metrics were developed for analyzing continuous 1-dimensional time-series. However, when dealing with spiking recordings from a neural population, we can transform the discrete, high-dimensional recordings into a 1-dimensional signal (as illustrated in the bottom panel of Figure 2). This transformation can be achieved by convolving the spikes from each neuron with an exponentially decaying kernel, mimicking a postsynaptic potential triggered by each spike. Subsequently, the convolved spikes can be averaged over the population of neurons for each time point, resulting in a synthetic 1-dimensional local field potential (sLFP) suitable for neural complexity analysis. An advantage of this approach is its ability to regulate the sources influencing the field potential, thus mitigating the impact of external variables unrelated to spiking activity, such as EMG contamination and volume-conducted signals (Buzsáki et al., 2012; Torres et al., 2019).

Having defined a way to measure neural complexity in field and spike recordings (Fig. 2), we can now show that this analysis bridges the different neural scales. To this end we compared ECoG (electrocorticography, also referred to as intracranial EEGs), LFPs and sLFPs recordings from frontal areas in freely behaving rats. By focusing on the low-frequency bands (filtering all signals between below 13 Hz), our results suggest that neural complexity differences remains relatively stable within each brain state, regardless of the scale at which it is analyzed (Fig. 3A). In other words, we found that the neural complexity differences across states were robustly maintained in all three recording scales. This result suggests that the intricacy of neural dynamics and its changes across the sleep-wake cycle are preserved across various levels of neuronal organization, from individual ensembles to broader cortical networks.

To gain a deeper understanding of why changes in neural complexity are consistent across different scales, we conducted an analysis of the microscopic (spiking) patterns underlying these changes. Our investigation revealed that periods of reduced firing, known as DOWN states (Isomura et al., 2006; Levenstein et al., 2019; Steriade et al., 1993) or OFF periods (Cavelli et al., 2023; Nir et al., 2011; Vyazovskiy et al., 2009), were responsible for the observed decrease in complexity in both synthetic local field potentials (sLFP) and traditional local field potentials (LFPs) during NREM sleep (Fig. 3B). This finding was evidenced by the observation that the removal of these periods prevented the decrease in complexity during NREM sleep. It is noteworthy that these DOWN states manifested as slow wave activity in LFPs and likely in ECoG recordings as well. Thus, our findings offer valuable insights into the propagation of microscopic activity across different scales.

Figure 3. Bridging the scales through the use of complexity metrics. **A** Permutation Minimum-Entropy (PME) across recording scales. From top to bottom, ECoG, LFP, synthetic LFP (obtained by the convolution of the spike trains and a decreasing exponential kernel), and units (spikes from individual neurons recorded from the extracellular medium). ECoG data comes from our experiments, but the other recordings come from the work by (Watson et al., 2016) (data-set available

at: CRCNS.org). Note that we inverted both LFP and ECoG recordings for representation purposes. Box plots show PME values for the ECoGs, LFPs, and sLFPs data-sets. * Modified from (González et al., 2022). **B Top:** Example of LFP and spiking activity in the neocortex exhibiting DOWN states (shown by pink boxes) during SWS. **Bottom:** Boxplots of Sample Entropy (top), Permutation Entropy (middle), and Lempel-Ziv Complexity (bottom) of the sLFPs and LFPs in each state (N = 24 sessions). * $p < 0.05$, ** $p < 0.01$, *** = $p < 0.001$. SWS Up-only was obtained by concatenating SWS UP periods only (excluding all down states). Modified from (González et al., 2023).

Drugs that alter consciousness disrupt neural complexity

In the previous section, we argued that the neural complexity differences between sleep-wake states are conserved across neural scales. To give further biological meaning to this quantity, we will next show that we can externally perturb neural complexity by administering drugs that alter consciousness. Moreover, we are going to argue how studying neural complexity can unveil functional convergence in the action of two unrelated drugs.

Figure 4. Ibogaine and urethane decrease neural complexity. **A.** Location of the analyzed intracranial electrodes in the right hemisphere (OB, olfactory bulb; M1, primary motor cortex; S1, primary somatosensory cortex; V2, secondary visual cortex). Either ibogaine (40 mg/Kg) or urethane (1.2-1.5 mg/Kg) were administered intraperitoneally. **B.** Top: Control (blue) and ibogaine (red) wake states (signal downsampled to 256 Hz) are shown. Bottom: Permutation entropy was employed to quantify the ECoG temporal complexity for ibogaine recordings. Each dot shows the average permutation entropy of an animal ($n = 6$). Bars represent mean \pm S.E.M. * $p < 0.05$, paired t test. **C.** For the urethane experiments, LZC was computed for frequencies between 1 and 195 Hz during wakefulness (W) and the anesthetized states (NREM-like urethane, NREMure; REM-like urethane,

REMure) for each electrode localization in the right hemisphere. * indicates significant differences. Modified from (González et al., 2021) (Mondino et al., 2022).

On one hand, ibogaine, an atypical psychedelic, has gained popularity for its ability to induce long-lasting antiaddictive effects (Köck et al., 2022). However, its mechanisms of action remain incompletely understood and involve several neurotransmitter systems (Mash, 2023), including the action of an active metabolite (Baumann et al., 2000; Castro-Nin et al., 2023). Our findings indicate that systemic administration of ibogaine promotes a waking state characterized by a gamma frequency band (30-100 Hz) profile that resembles REM sleep (González et al., 2021, 2018). On the other hand, urethane is a commonly used anesthetic in animal research, which induces two alternating anesthetic states: NREMure and REMure (Hara and Harris, 2002). Although these states are often used as pharmacological models of sleep (Hay et al., 2021; Pagliardini et al., 2013), they differ significantly from natural sleep states (Mondino et al., 2022). Its mechanisms of action involve a wide array of targets but, unlike ibogaine, ultimately results in unconsciousness.

Crucially, despite the contrasting mechanisms and effects of the drugs (where ibogaine enhances gamma activity while urethane diminishes it), both ibogaine and urethane administration resulted in reduced neural complexity across the brain (Fig. 4). This finding suggests that brain activity becomes less diverse during the acute effects of both drugs. It's worth noting that urethane, especially in the synchronized state (referred to as NREMure in Fig. 4), seemed to induce more pronounced complexity changes compared to ibogaine. Hence, these examples illustrate how two drugs profoundly affecting cognition also disrupt neural complexity.

The way up: how microscopic changes affect global brain states.

Finally, we show by proof of concept how manipulating the microscopic level can impact macroscopic dynamics. These types of experiments and analyses can also help us understand which factors determine and influence neural complexity. For this example, we will see how a specific group of glutamatergic neurons in the preoptic area of the hypothalamus not only controlled sleep state transitions but also neural complexity in each state.

Noteworthy, the preoptic area of the hypothalamus is a crucial site for sleep generation, which projects diffusely into arousal centers across the brain (Vanini and Torterolo, 2021). While it has been historically considered an exclusive sleep promoting center, this notion has been challenged by theoretical models and experimental results. The emergent picture suggests that the preoptic area might play a dual role in sleep-wake control (Lombardi et al., 2020; Mondino et al., 2021; Vanini et al., 2020), initiating (but not maintaining) arousal to possibly prevent undesired REM sleep intrusions into NREM.

For this set of chemogenetic experiments (Mondino et al., 2021), the excitatory cre-dependent designer receptor hM3Dq was injected into the medial-lateral preoptic region of Vglut2-cre animals (Fig. 5A). As a result, only excitatory neurons expressed the designer receptor and could be activated by the systemic injection of a designer drug (in this case clozapine-n-oxide, CNO). When stimulated, this excitatory subgroup induced global state transitions and fragmented sleep. Remarkably, chemogenetic stimulation led to an increase

in neural complexity at the global cortical level (Fig. 5B). This increase in neural complexity occurred irrespective of the arousal state, as significant complexity increases were observed during both wakefulness and NREM sleep. In fact, complexity during NREM following chemogenetic stimulation reached similar levels to the unstimulated wakefulness. Hence, these findings suggest that changes at the microscopic level, such as alterations in the firing rate of a small subpopulation within a deep nucleus, can profoundly impact neural complexity at a different recording scale.

Figure 5. Going up: how microscopic changes affect global brain states. A Schematic representation of bilateral injections of a Cre-dependent adeno-associated virus for expression of the excitatory designer receptor hM3Dq into the medial-lateral preoptic region of Vglut2-Cre mice. Three weeks after the injection, mice were implanted with electrodes for recording the EEG from the right frontal (purple) and right occipital (yellow) cortex. A reference electrode was placed over the cerebellum (orange), and two electrodes were also implanted bilaterally in the neck muscles for recording the EMG. Representative EEG and EMG signals from a mouse during wakefulness, NREM sleep, and REM sleep. Below we show the cFos expression (green nuclei) in mCherry-positive (red) neurons in the medial-lateral preoptic region after CNO (1.0 mg/kg; n = 4 mice) and VEH (n = 4) administration. Brain image was modified from <https://neuroscience-graphicdesign.com/>. **B** Graphs plot showing neural complexity as assessed by corrected Lempel-Ziv complexity (cLZC) values during wakefulness (W) and NREM sleep for frontal and occipital regions. Data are mean \pm SEM. Differences between VEH and CNO (1.0 mg/kg) in n = 10 mice were analyzed by two-tailed paired t tests. *Significant difference ($p < 0.05$) relative to control. Modified from (Mondino et al., 2021).

Conclusions

The brain exhibits activity across multiple scales, from the macroscopic to the microscopic, highlighting its complexity. Complexity analysis offers a novel perspective for studying brain activity across scales. It provides a framework for navigating the intricate dynamics of neural networks, allowing researchers to uncover patterns and emergent phenomena that may not be apparent with traditional analytical approaches. Studying the effects of drugs on neural complexity can offer insights into common mechanisms of action at the macroscopic level.

Finally, understanding how changes at the microscopic scale, such as the firing patterns of individual neurons, affect macroscopic brain activity is crucial for unraveling the mechanisms underlying brain function. Such insights can provide a deeper understanding of how neural circuits process information and generate behavior.

Declarations of interest

All other authors state no conflict of interest.

Author contributions

JG and PT wrote the initial draft. All authors reviewed and edited it. All authors have accepted responsibility for the entire content of this manuscript and approved its submission.

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Data availability

The raw original data is available under request to the authors

References

- Abdelfattah, A.S., Kawashima, T., Singh, A., Novak, O., Liu, H., Shuai, Y., Huang, Y.-C., Campagnola, L., Seeman, S.C., Yu, J., Zheng, J., Grimm, J.B., Patel, R., Friedrich, J., Mensh, B.D., Paninski, L., Macklin, J.J., Murphy, G.J., Podgorski, K., Lin, B.-J., Chen, T.-W., Turner, G.C., Liu, Z., Koyama, M., Svoboda, K., Ahrens, M.B., Lavis, L.D., Schreier, E.R., 2019. Bright and photostable chemigenetic indicators for extended in vivo voltage imaging. *Science* 365, 699–704.
- Adamantidis, A.R., Zhang, F., Aravanis, A.M., Deisseroth, K., de Lecea, L., 2007. Neural substrates of awakening probed with optogenetic control of hypocretin neurons. *Nature* 450, 420–424.
- Bandt, C., Pompe, B., 2002. Permutation entropy: a natural complexity measure for time series. *Phys. Rev. Lett.* 88, 174102.
- Barabasi, A.L., Albert, R., 1999. Emergence of scaling in random networks. *Science* 286, 509–512.
- Baumann, M.H., Pablo, J.P., Ali, S.F., Rothman, R.B., Mash, D.C., 2000. Noribogaine (12-hydroxyibogamine): a biologically active metabolite of the antiaddictive drug ibogaine. *Ann. N. Y. Acad. Sci.* 914, 354–368.
- Beggs, J.M., Plenz, D., 2003. Neuronal avalanches in neocortical circuits. *J. Neurosci.* 23, 11167–11177.
- Bellay, T., Klaus, A., Seshadri, S., Plenz, D., 2015. Irregular spiking of pyramidal neurons organizes as scale-invariant neuronal avalanches in the awake state. *Elife* 4, e07224.
- Berger, H., 1929. Über das Elektrenkephalogramm des Menschen. *Archiv für Psychiatrie und Nervenkrankheiten* 87, 527–570.
- Biasiucci, A., Franceschiello, B., Murray, M.M., 2019. Electroencephalography. *Curr. Biol.* 29, R80–R85.
- Binzegger, T., Douglas, R.J., Martin, K.A.C., 2004. A quantitative map of the circuit of cat primary visual cortex. *J. Neurosci.* 24, 8441–8453.

- Bohara, G., West, B.J., Grigolini, P., 2018. Bridging Waves and Crucial Events in the Dynamics of the Brain. *Front. Physiol.* 9, 1174.
- Buzsáki, G., 2004. Large-scale recording of neuronal ensembles. *Nat. Neurosci.* 7, 446–451.
- Buzsáki, G., Anastassiou, C.A., Koch, C., 2012. The origin of extracellular fields and currents—EEG, ECoG, LFP and spikes. *Nat. Rev. Neurosci.* 13, 407–420.
- Buzsáki, G., Draguhn, A., 2004. Neuronal oscillations in cortical networks. *Science* 304, 1926–1929.
- Buzsáki, G., Wang, X.-J., 2012. Mechanisms of gamma oscillations. *Annu. Rev. Neurosci.* 35, 203–225.
- Casali, A.G., Gosseries, O., Rosanova, M., Boly, M., Sarasso, S., Casali, K.R., Casarotto, S., Bruno, M.-A., Laureys, S., Tononi, G., Massimini, M., 2013. A theoretically based index of consciousness independent of sensory processing and behavior. *Sci. Transl. Med.* 5, 198ra105.
- Castro-Nin, J.P., Serantes, D., Rodriguez, P., Gonzalez, B., Carrera, I., Torterolo, P., González, J., 2023. Noribogaine effects on wakefulness and sleep. *bioRxiv*. <https://doi.org/10.1101/2023.07.26.550725>
- Cavelli, M.L., Mao, R., Findlay, G., Driessen, K., Bugnon, T., Tononi, G., Cirelli, C., 2023. Sleep/wake changes in perturbational complexity in rats and mice. *iScience* 26, 106186.
- Chialvo, D.R., 2010. Emergent complex neural dynamics. *Nat. Phys.* 6, 744–750.
- Donoghue, T., Haller, M., Peterson, E.J., Varma, P., Sebastian, P., Gao, R., Noto, T., Lara, A.H., Wallis, J.D., Knight, R.T., Shestyuk, A., Voytek, B., 2020. Parameterizing neural power spectra into periodic and aperiodic components. *Nat. Neurosci.* 23, 1655–1665.
- Douglas, R.J., Martin, K.A.C., 2004. Neuronal circuits of the neocortex. *Annu. Rev. Neurosci.* 27, 419–451.
- Fernández-Ruiz, A., Oliva, A., Soula, M., Rocha-Almeida, F., Nagy, G.A., Martin-Vazquez, G., Buzsáki, G., 2021. Gamma rhythm communication between entorhinal cortex and dentate gyrus neuronal assemblies. *Science* 372. <https://doi.org/10.1126/science.abf3119>
- Fontenele, A.J., de Vasconcelos, N.A.P., Feliciano, T., Aguiar, L.A.A., Soares-Cunha, C., Coimbra, B., Dalla Porta, L., Ribeiro, S., Rodrigues, A.J., Sousa, N., Carelli, P.V., Copelli, M., 2019. Criticality between Cortical States. *Phys. Rev. Lett.* 122, 208101.
- Friston, K., 2005. A theory of cortical responses. *Philos. Trans. R. Soc. Lond. B Biol. Sci.* 360, 815–836.
- Gao, P., Ganguli, S., 2015. On simplicity and complexity in the brave new world of large-scale neuroscience. *Curr. Opin. Neurobiol.* 32, 148–155.
- González, J., Cavelli, M., Castro-Zaballa, S., Mondino, A., Tort, A.B.L., Rubido, N., Carrera, I., Torterolo, P., 2021. EEG Gamma Band Alterations and REM-like Traits Underpin the Acute Effect of the Atypical Psychedelic Ibogaine in the Rat. *ACS Pharmacol Transl Sci* 4, 517–525.
- González, J., Cavelli, M., Mondino, A., Pascovich, C., Castro-Zaballa, S., Torterolo, P., Rubido, N., 2019. Decreased electrocortical temporal complexity distinguishes sleep from wakefulness. *Sci. Rep.* 9, 18457.
- González, J., Cavelli, M., Mondino, A., Rubido, N., BI Tort, A., Torterolo, P., 2020. Communication Through Coherence by Means of Cross-frequency Coupling. *Neuroscience* 449, 157–164.
- González, J., Cavelli, M., Tort, A.B.L., Torterolo, P., Rubido, N., 2023. Sleep disrupts complex spiking dynamics in the neocortex and hippocampus. *PLoS One* 18, e0290146.
- González, J., Mateos, D., Cavelli, M., Mondino, A., Pascovich, C., Torterolo, P., Rubido, N., 2022. Low frequency oscillations drive EEG's complexity changes during wakefulness and sleep. *Neuroscience* 494, 1–11.
- González, J., Prieto, J.P., Rodríguez, P., Cavelli, M., Benedetto, L., Mondino, A., Pazos, M., Seoane, G., Carrera, I., Scorza, C., Torterolo, P., 2018. Ibogaine Acute Administration in Rats Promotes Wakefulness, Long-Lasting REM Sleep Suppression, and a Distinctive Motor Profile. *Front. Pharmacol.* 9, 374.
- Gonzalez, J., Torterolo, P., Tort, A.B.L., 2023. Mechanisms and functions of

- respiration-driven gamma oscillations in the primary olfactory cortex. *Elife* 12. <https://doi.org/10.7554/eLife.83044>
- Grinvald, A., Hildesheim, R., 2004. VSDI: a new era in functional imaging of cortical dynamics. *Nat. Rev. Neurosci.* 5, 874–885.
- Hara, K., Harris, R.A., 2002. The anesthetic mechanism of urethane: the effects on neurotransmitter-gated ion channels. *Anesth. Analg.* 94, 313–8, table of contents.
- Hay, Y.A., Deperrois, N., Fuchsberger, T., Quarrell, T.M., Koerling, A.-L., Paulsen, O., 2021. Thalamus mediates neocortical Down state transition via GABA-receptor-targeting interneurons. *Neuron* 109, 2682–2690.e5.
- He, B.J., Raichle, M.E., 2009. The fMRI signal, slow cortical potential and consciousness. *Trends Cogn. Sci.* 13, 302–309.
- Herreras, O., 2016. Local Field Potentials: Myths and Misunderstandings. *Front. Neural Circuits* 10, 101.
- Huang, S.Y., Witzel, T., Keil, B., Scholz, A., Davids, M., Dietz, P., Rummert, E., Ramb, R., Kirsch, J.E., Yendiki, A., Fan, Q., Tian, Q., Ramos-Llorden, G., Lee, H.-H., Nummenmaa, A., Bilgic, B., Setsompop, K., Wang, F., Avram, A.V., Komlosh, M., Benjamin, D., Magdoom, K.N., Pathak, S., Schneider, W., Novikov, D.S., Fieremans, E., Tounekti, S., Mekkaoui, C., Augustinack, J., Berger, D., Shapson-Coe, A., Lichtman, J., Basser, P.J., Wald, L.L., Rosen, B.R., 2021. Connectome 2.0: Developing the next-generation ultra-high gradient strength human MRI scanner for bridging studies of the micro-, meso- and macro-connectome. *Neuroimage* 243, 118530.
- Isomura, Y., Sirota, A., Ozen, S., Montgomery, S., Mizuseki, K., Henze, D.A., Buzsáki, G., 2006. Integration and segregation of activity in entorhinal-hippocampal subregions by neocortical slow oscillations. *Neuron* 52, 871–882.
- Jun, J.J., Steinmetz, N.A., Siegle, J.H., Denman, D.J., Bauza, M., Barbarits, B., Lee, A.K., Anastassiou, C.A., Andrei, A., Aydin, Ç., Barbic, M., Blanche, T.J., Bonin, V., Couto, J., Dutta, B., Gratiy, S.L., Gutnisky, D.A., Häusser, M., Karsh, B., Ledochowitsch, P., Lopez, C.M., Mitelut, C., Musa, S., Okun, M., Pachitariu, M., Putzeys, J., Rich, P.D., Rossant, C., Sun, W.-L., Svoboda, K., Carandini, M., Harris, K.D., Koch, C., O’Keefe, J., Harris, T.D., 2017. Fully integrated silicon probes for high-density recording of neural activity. *Nature* 551, 232–236.
- Kiebel, S.J., Daunizeau, J., Friston, K.J., 2008. A hierarchy of time-scales and the brain. *PLoS Comput. Biol.* 4, e1000209.
- Köck, P., Froelich, K., Walter, M., Lang, U., Dürsteler, K.M., 2022. A systematic literature review of clinical trials and therapeutic applications of ibogaine. *J. Subst. Abuse Treat.* 138, 108717.
- Lee, S.-H., Dan, Y., 2012. Neuromodulation of brain states. *Neuron* 76, 209–222.
- Lempel, A., Ziv, J., 1976. On the complexity of finite sequences. *IEEE Trans. Inf. Theory* 22, 75–81.
- Lendner, J.D., Helfrich, R.F., Mander, B.A., Romundstad, L., Lin, J.J., Walker, M.P., Larsson, P.G., Knight, R.T., 2020. An electrophysiological marker of arousal level in humans. *Elife* 9. <https://doi.org/10.7554/eLife.55092>
- Levenstein, D., Buzsáki, G., Rinzal, J., 2019. NREM sleep in the rodent neocortex and hippocampus reflects excitable dynamics. *Nat. Commun.* 10, 2478.
- Lewis, C.M., Bosman, C.A., Fries, P., 2015. Recording of brain activity across spatial scales. *Curr. Opin. Neurobiol.* 32, 68–77.
- Lewis, C.M., Hoffmann, A., Helmchen, F., 2024. Linking brain activity across scales with simultaneous opto- and electrophysiology. *Neurophotonics* 11, 033403.
- Lombardi, F., Gómez-Extremera, M., Bernal-Galván, P., Vetrivelan, R., Saper, C.B., Scammell, T.E., Ivanov, P.C., 2020. Critical Dynamics and Coupling in Bursts of Cortical Rhythms Indicate Non-Homeostatic Mechanism for Sleep-Stage Transitions and Dual Role of VLPO Neurons in Both Sleep and Wake. *J. Neurosci.* 40, 171–190.
- Luo, L., 2021. Architectures of neuronal circuits. *Science* 373, eabg7285.
- Mash, D.C., 2023. IUPHAR - invited review - Ibogaine - A legacy within the current renaissance of psychedelic therapy. *Pharmacol. Res.* 190, 106620.

- Massimini, M., Ferrarelli, F., Huber, R., Esser, S.K., Singh, H., Tononi, G., 2005. Breakdown of cortical effective connectivity during sleep. *Science* 309, 2228–2232.
- Massimini, M., Huber, R., Ferrarelli, F., Hill, S., Tononi, G., 2004. The sleep slow oscillation as a traveling wave. *J. Neurosci.* 24, 6862–6870.
- Mateos, D., Zozor, S., Olivares, F., 2020. Contrasting stochasticity with chaos in a permutation Lempel–Ziv complexity — Shannon entropy plane. *Physica A: Statistical Mechanics and its Applications* 554, 124640.
- Miller, K.J., Sorensen, L.B., Ojemann, J.G., den Nijs, M., 2009. Power-Law Scaling in the Brain Surface Electric Potential. *PLoS Comput. Biol.* 5, e1000609.
- Mondino, A., Cavelli, M., González, J., Osorio, L., Castro-Zaballa, S., Costa, A., Vanini, G., Torterolo, P., 2020. Power and Coherence in the EEG of the Rat: Impact of Behavioral States, Cortical Area, Lateralization and Light/Dark Phases. *Clocks Sleep* 2, 536–556.
- Mondino, A., González, J., Li, D., Mateos, D., Osorio, L., Cavelli, M., Castro-Nin, J.P., Serantes, D., Costa, A., Vanini, G., Mashour, G.A., Torterolo, P., 2022. Urethane anaesthesia exhibits neurophysiological correlates of unconsciousness and is distinct from sleep. *Eur. J. Neurosci.* <https://doi.org/10.1111/ejn.15690>
- Mondino, A., Hambrecht-Wiedbusch, V.S., Li, D., York, A.K., Pal, D., González, J., Torterolo, P., Mashour, G.A., Vanini, G., 2021. Glutamatergic Neurons in the Preoptic Hypothalamus Promote Wakefulness, Destabilize NREM Sleep, Suppress REM Sleep, and Regulate Cortical Dynamics. *J. Neurosci.* 41, 3462–3478.
- Munn, B.R., Müller, E.J., Medel, V., Naismith, S.L., Lizier, J.T., Sanders, R.D., Shine, J.M., 2023. Neuronal connected burst cascades bridge macroscale adaptive signatures across arousal states. *Nat. Commun.* 14, 1–17.
- Nir, Y., de Lecea, L., 2023. Sleep and vigilance states: Embracing spatiotemporal dynamics. *Neuron* 111, 1998–2011.
- Nir, Y., Staba, R.J., Andrillon, T., Vyazovskiy, V.V., Cirelli, C., Fried, I., Tononi, G., 2011. Regional slow waves and spindles in human sleep. *Neuron* 70, 153–169.
- Ogawa, S., Lee, T.M., Kay, A.R., Tank, D.W., 1990. Brain magnetic resonance imaging with contrast dependent on blood oxygenation. *Proc. Natl. Acad. Sci. U. S. A.* 87, 9868–9872.
- Pagliardini, S., Funk, G.D., Dickson, C.T., 2013. Breathing and brain state: urethane anesthesia as a model for natural sleep. *Respir. Physiol. Neurobiol.* 188, 324–332.
- Paninski, L., Cunningham, J.P., 2018. Neural data science: accelerating the experiment-analysis-theory cycle in large-scale neuroscience. *Curr. Opin. Neurobiol.* 50, 232–241.
- Pascovich, C., Castro-Zaballa, S., Mediano, P.A.M., Bor, D., Canales-Johnson, A., Torterolo, P., Bekinschtein, T.A., 2022. Ketamine and sleep modulate neural complexity dynamics in cats. *Eur. J. Neurosci.* 55, 1584–1600.
- Priesemann, V., Valderrama, M., Wibral, M., Le Van Quyen, M., 2013. Neuronal avalanches differ from wakefulness to deep sleep—evidence from intracranial depth recordings in humans. *PLoS Comput. Biol.* 9, e1002985.
- Priesemann, V., Wibral, M., Valderrama, M., Pröpper, R., Le Van Quyen, M., Geisel, T., Triesch, J., Nikolić, D., Munk, M.H.J., 2014. Spike avalanches in vivo suggest a driven, slightly subcritical brain state. *Front. Syst. Neurosci.* 8, 108.
- Ribeiro, T.L., Copelli, M., Caixeta, F., Belchior, H., Chialvo, D.R., Nicolelis, M.A.L., Ribeiro, S., 2010. Spike avalanches exhibit universal dynamics across the sleep-wake cycle. *PLoS One* 5, e14129.
- Sakmann, B., Neher, E., 1984. Patch clamp techniques for studying ionic channels in excitable membranes. *Annu. Rev. Physiol.* 46, 455–472.
- Scholtens, L.H., van den Heuvel, M.P., 2018. Multimodal Connectomics in Psychiatry: Bridging Scales From Micro to Macro. *Biol Psychiatry Cogn Neurosci Neuroimaging* 3, 767–776.
- Sejnowski, T.J., Churchland, P.S., Movshon, J.A., 2014. Putting big data to good use in neuroscience. *Nat. Neurosci.* 17, 1440–1441.
- Sporns, O., Tononi, G., Kötter, R., 2005. The human connectome: A structural description of

- the human brain. *PLoS Comput. Biol.* 1, e42.
- Steinmetz, N.A., Zatka-Haas, P., Carandini, M., Harris, K.D., 2019. Distributed coding of choice, action and engagement across the mouse brain. *Nature* 576, 266–273.
- Steriade, M., Nuñez, A., Amzica, F., 1993. Intracellular analysis of relations between the slow (< 1 Hz) neocortical oscillation and other sleep rhythms of the electroencephalogram. *J. Neurosci.* 13, 3266–3283.
- Stern, M., Bolding, K.A., Abbott, L.F., Franks, K.M., 2018. A transformation from temporal to ensemble coding in a model of piriform cortex. *Elife* 7. <https://doi.org/10.7554/eLife.34831>
- Stringer, C., Pachitariu, M., Steinmetz, N., Carandini, M., Harris, K.D., 2019a. High-dimensional geometry of population responses in visual cortex. *Nature* 571, 361–365.
- Stringer, C., Pachitariu, M., Steinmetz, N., Reddy, C.B., Carandini, M., Harris, K.D., 2019b. Spontaneous behaviors drive multidimensional, brainwide activity. *Science* 364, 255.
- Tian, L., Hires, S.A., Mao, T., Huber, D., Chiappe, M.E., Chalasani, S.H., Petreanu, L., Akerboom, J., McKinney, S.A., Schreier, E.R., Bargmann, C.I., Jayaraman, V., Svoboda, K., Looger, L.L., 2009. Imaging neural activity in worms, flies and mice with improved GCaMP calcium indicators. *Nat. Methods* 6, 875–881.
- Tononi, G., Sporns, O., Edelman, G.M., 1994. A measure for brain complexity: relating functional segregation and integration in the nervous system. *Proc. Natl. Acad. Sci. U. S. A.* 91, 5033–5037.
- Torres, D., Makarova, J., Ortuño, T., Benito, N., Makarov, V.A., Herreras, O., 2019. Local and Volume-Conducted Contributions to Cortical Field Potentials. *Cereb. Cortex* 29, 5234–5254.
- Tort, A.B.L., Komorowski, R.W., Manns, J.R., Kopell, N.J., Eichenbaum, H., 2009. Theta-gamma coupling increases during the learning of item-context associations. *Proc. Natl. Acad. Sci. U. S. A.* 106, 20942–20947.
- Vanini, G., Bassana, M., Mast, M., Mondino, A., Cerda, I., Phyle, M., Chen, V., Colmenero, A.V., Hambrecht-Wiedbusch, V.S., Mashour, G.A., 2020. Activation of Preoptic GABAergic or Glutamatergic Neurons Modulates Sleep-Wake Architecture, but Not Anesthetic State Transitions. *Curr. Biol.* 30, 779–787.e4.
- Vanini, G., Torterolo, P., 2021. Sleep-Wake Neurobiology. *Adv. Exp. Med. Biol.* 1297, 65–82.
- Vyazovskiy, V.V., Olcese, U., Lazimy, Y.M., Faraguna, U., Esser, S.K., Williams, J.C., Cirelli, C., Tononi, G., 2009. Cortical firing and sleep homeostasis. *Neuron* 63, 865–878.
- Watson, B.O., Levenstein, D., Greene, J.P., Gelinás, J.N., Buzsáki, G., 2016. Network Homeostasis and State Dynamics of Neocortical Sleep. *Neuron* 90, 839–852.
- Williamson, R.C., Doiron, B., Smith, M.A., Yu, B.M., 2019. Bridging large-scale neuronal recordings and large-scale network models using dimensionality reduction. *Curr. Opin. Neurobiol.* 55, 40–47.